

APÊNDICE C - LISTA DE ARTIGOS ACEITOS DA LITERATURA

ID	Título	Ano de publicação	Autores
E1	The Human Side of Software Engineering Teams: An Investigation of Contemporary Challenges	2023	Marco Hoffmann , Daniel Mendez , Fabian Fagerholm , and Anton Luckhardt
E2	Remote Persons Are Closer Than They Appear: Home, Team and a Lockdown	2023	Mirjam Augstein, Thomas Neumayr, Johannes Schönböck e Carrie Ko
E3	The Other Side of Turnover: Managing IT Personnel Strategically	2005	Havard Meland,Rolf Petter Waage,Maung K. Sein
E4	Exploring the Role of Mentoring in the IS Profession: A Cross-National Comparison	2012	Monica Adya,John Cotton
E5	Career Orientation and Organizational Commitment of IT Personnel	2005	Mary Sumner Southern, Susan Yager Southern , Denise Franke University
E6	Stay or Quit: IT Personnel Turnover in Botswana	2011	F.M.E. Uzoka,K.V. Mgaya, A. P Shemi, B.A. Akinnuwesi
E7	Employee Retention and Turnover in Global Software Development: Comparing in-House Offshoring and Offshore Outsourcing	2018	Julian M. Bass, Sarah Beecham
E8	A Project Management Framework for Global Software Development	2018	Ritu Jain,Ugrasen Suman

E9	Antecedents of Turnover Intention and Actual Turnover among Information Systems Personnel in South Africa	2006	Derek Smith,H. L. Speight
E10	Globally Distributed Teams: The Effect of Diversity on Trust, Cohesion and Individual Performance	2010	Gary Garrison,Robin L. Wakefield,Xiaobo Xu,Sang Hyun Kim
E11	Developer Turnover in Global, Industrial Open Source Projects: Insights from Applying Survival Analysis	2017	Bin Lin,Gregorio Robles,Alexander Serebrenik
E12	Voluntary Turnover in a Distributed Work Setting: An Examination of the Role of Spatial Proximity and Role Similarity in Project Affiliation Networks	2013	Gopakumar Gopalakrishnan,Daniel S. Halgin,,Stephen P. Borgatti
E13	Turnover in Open-Source Projects: The Case of Core Developers	2020	Fabio Ferreira,Luciana Lourdes Silva,Marco Tulio Valente
E14	How Temporal Work Styles and Product Modularity Influence Software Quality and Job Satisfaction	2016	Jens Foerderer,Thomas Kude,Sunil Mithas,Armin Heinzl
E15	Spaces of IT Intrapreneurial Freedom: A Classic Grounded Theory	2013	Gaetan Mourmant,Fred Niederman ,Michel Kalika
E16	Turnover of Information Technology Professionals: The Effects of Internal Labor Market Strategies	2004	Soon Ang N,Sandra Slaughter

E17	A Qualitative Study of the Determinants of Self-Managing Team Effectiveness in a Scrum Team	2011	Cleviton V. F. Monteiro, Fabio Q. B. da Silva, Isabella R. M. dos Santos, Felipe Farias, Elisa S. F. Cardozo, André R. G. do A. Leitão, Dacio N. M. Neto, Miguel J. A. Pernambuco Filho
E18	Examining IT Professionals' Adaptation to Technological Change: The Influence of Gender and Personal Attributes	2004	Michael J. Gallivan
E19	What Causes Stress in Information System Professionals?	2004	Vikram Sethi, Ruth C. King, and James Campbell Quick
E20	How Human and Organizational Factors Influence Software Teams Productivity in COVID-19 Pandemic: A Brazilian Survey	2020	Carla I. M. Bezerra, José Cezar de Souza Filho*, Emanuel F. Coutinho, Alice Gama, Ana Livia Ferreira, Gabriel Leitão de Andrade, Carlos Eduardo Feitosa
E21	The Politics of Emotion: Exploring Emotional Labor and Political Skill across Job Types within the IT/IS Profession	2015	Paige Rutner, Feruzan Irani Williams, Constance Campbell, Cynthia K. Riemenschneider
E22	IT Workforce Planning: A Modular Design Science Approach	2011	Monica Adya, Fred Niederman

E23	Examining Career Orientations of Information Systems Personnel in an Emerging Economy Context	2009	K. V. Mgaya
E24	Single- And Double-Loop Learning: Linking Free/Libre Open Source Software (FLOSS) Developer Motivation, Contribution, and Turnover Intentions	2020	Sherae Daniel, Shadi Jananefat, E. Ilana Diamant, Yuqing Ren
E25	The moderating roles of technological self-efficacy and time management in the technostress and employee performance relationship through burnout	2021	Serdar Yener, Aykut Arslan, Sebahattin Kiliç
E26	When Agile Means Staying: A Moderated Mediated Model	2020	Tenace Kwaku Setor
E27	Should I stay or should I go? A study of IT professionals during a national crisis	2019	Carlo Gabriel Porto Bellini, Prashant Palvia, Valter Moreno, Tim Jacks, Alexandre Graeml
E28	When agile means staying: The relationship between agile development usage and individual IT professional outcomes	2019	Tenace Setor, Damien Joseph
E29	An empirical study on using agile methods in global software development	2018	V. N. Vithana#1, D. Asirvatham *2, M.G.M. Johar #3
E30	How temporal work styles and product modularity influence software quality and job satisfaction	2016	Jens Foerderer, Thomas Kude, Sunil Mithas, Armin Heinzl
E31	Continuous Software Testing in a Globally Distributed Project	2015	Nils Brede Moe, Daniela Cruzes, Tore Dybå, Edda Mikkelsen

E32	A global perspective on information systems personnel turnover	2010	Hoon S. Cha, Jing Quan
E33	IT certifications, outsourcing and information systems personnel turnover		Jing Quan and Hoon Cha
E34	Off-site commitment and voluntary turnover in GSD projects	2010	Peitsa Hynninen, Arttu Piri and Tuomas Niinimäki
E35	Turnover intentions of Indian IS professionals	2008	Mary C. Lacity & Vidya V. Iyer & Prasad S. Rudramuniyaiah
E36	Information technology and the autonomy-control duality: Toward a theory	2007	Ali Tafti, Sunil Mithas, M. S. Krishnan
E37	Exploring the effects of trust, task interdependence and virtualness on knowledge sharing in teams	2008	D. Sandy Staples, Jane Webster
E38	The advancement and persistence of women in the information technology profession: An extension of Ahuja's gendered theory of IT career stages	2017	Deborah J. Armstrong, Cynthia K. Riemenschneider, Laurie G. Giddens
E39	What {Motivates} {Software} {Engineers} {Working} in {Global} {Software} {Development}?	2015	Sarah Beecham, John Noil
E40	Motivating Software Engineers Working in Virtual Teams Across the Globe	2014	Sarah Beecham
E41	Investigating the Relationship between Software Team Leadership Styles and Turnover Intention	2022	Narallynne Araújo, Tiago Massoni, Camila Sarmiento, Francielle Santos, Ruan Oliveira

E42	A Deep Dive into the Impact of COVID-19 on Software Development	2022	Paulo Anselmo da Mota Silveira Neto , Umme Ayda Mannan , Eduardo Santana de Almeida , Senior Member, IEEE, Nachiappan Nagappan, Fellow, IEEE, David Lo , Pavneet Singh Kochhar, Cuiyun Gao , and Iftekhar Ahmed
E43	The Influence of Workplace Social Support on IT Professionals' Turnover Intention during the COVID-19 Crisis	2021	Barbara Prommegger, Helmut Krömer
E44	A Proposed Model for Predicting Employee Turnover of Information Technology Specialists Using Data Mining Techniques	2021	Ahmed Hosny Ghazi, Samir Ismail Elsayed, Ayman Elsayed Khedr
E45	Satisfaction of IT Professionals with Employment Arrangements in Traditional and Virtual Contexts	2001	Thomas W. Ferratt, Harvey G. Enns, Jayesh Prasad
E46	A Proposed Model for Predicting Employee Turnover of Information Technology Specialists Using Data Mining Techniques	2021	Ghazi, Ahmed Hosny and Elsayed, Samir Ismail and Khedr, Elsayed Ayman